

Victor Team Description Paper

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Abstract: Soccer Simulation 2D League is one of the major leagues of RoboCup competitions. In a Soccer Simulation 2D (SS2D) game, two teams of 11 players and one coach compete against each other. The players are only allowed to communicate with the server that is called Soccer Simulation **Server**. Two-dimensional simulation is a football space that is simulated from real football, and the two dimensions x and y are meant. From the beginning of the game, each player sends 1 message to the server on each cycle, which means that by the end of the game, 6000 messages will be sent to the server from each player.

Keywords: Two-dimensional simulation (2D) . cycle . Soccer Simulation .

Introduction : Our team is Victor. We started our training in November 1401 and started the group activity from January 1402. Our group hopes to be able to rank well in 2D football simulation matches by relying on the team's abilities.

1 Major Behaviors During Attack

1.1 Pass

In the pass, we give points according to the position of the player and whether there is an opponent player or not. Whoever has more points, we must pass him. In this code, we draw a rectangle and check if there is an opponent player there or not. Our rectangle consists of two nested triangles, one of them is in the base code. But we also defined another triangle too, which is a teammate is at the top of that and in the other sides the player who owns the ball, stands.

Correct pass modes

1.2 Shoot

One of the important parts in football is shooting. The players procedure for shooting is as follows: if the goalkeeper is on the left side of the goal, the player should not shoot to the left side of the goal, he should shoot to the right side of the goal. shoot, and also if the goalkeeper is on the right side of the goal, the player must shoot to the left side of the goal. Also, an angle is determined that if the opponents distance is less than the determined angle, do not shoot, and if the distance is greater Shoot it.

The right way to shoot.

1.3 Dribble:

Dribble is a special technique in football but using that in 2D shematic form is a bit difficult and it has some limits Victor's group try to improve themselves in this technique and be one of the best In this part we consider the situation of doing dribble Imagine that our player can catch the ball and a player of another team against him Now he should increase his speed and change his course to continue the game so finally he would shoot the ball in a net The player imaginary draw a circle with tree segment .After that he match tree specific dot on the circle to make a trigle Then he draw a new triangle on each side of primary triangle So finally it would be a hexagon in general circle At the end when anyone from another team came into one of this triangle ,our player should avoid him.

1.4 Clear ball

This behavior is a type of defensive behavior that is used when the ball is in the hand of an insider player inside penalty area and the opponent's player is close and may pose a danger by taking the ball from us, and for this reason, we wil move the ball away. One of the algorithms is that we send the ball to the nearest out line. In this algorithm, we tried to first check thedistance of the opponent from the ball (ourselves) and choose a route where the opponnet can receive the ball later. We divide our field into two parts and based on the position of the ball relative to the

D. ebadi et al

opponent, we target sending the ball to the nearest sideline. It is important to check the distance of the teammate to our coordinates before doing this behavior.

2 Squad and Layout:

The combination we use is **4-3-3** and the reason is that the team is neither completely aggressive nor defensive.

Combine players at the start of the game

Future Work

We hope that next year's tournament will be able to get better rankings with a stronger team better ideas †hanks to everyone who helped us in this regard.

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